

Parametric excitation of a conical pendulum

Masters Thesis in Physics

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Thanks to my advisor Prof. Krishna Kumar who was always there for me whenever I needed help. Without his valuable discussions and suggestions, I would not have gotten so far in this project.

Declaration

I declare that this written submission represents my ideas in my own words and where other ideas or words have been included, I have adequately cited and referenced the original sources. I also declare that I have adhered to all principles of academic honesty and integrity and have not misrepresented or falsified any ideas/data/facts/sources in my submission. I understand that any violation of the above will be cause for disciplinary action by the institute and can also invoke penal action from the sources which have not been properly cited or from whom proper permission has not been taken when needed.

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BONA FIDE CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “ Parametric excitations of a conical pendulum ” submitted to the Department of Physics, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur 721302, India for the partial fulfillment of the M.Sc. Degree in Physics, embodies bona fide work done by Faizan Hilal Lone under my supervision at Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur. This work has not been submitted in part or full for any other degree or diploma of any other institute.

kkumar 04.06.2020

Prof. K. Kumar
(Project Supervisor)

Introduction

A practical conical pendulum consists of a bob fixed at one end of a light rod, whose other end is suspended from a pivot. The light rod moves on a cone and its bob traces a circle with constant speed in a horizontal plane. A conical pendulum [1] was first studied by Robert Hooke more than 350 years ago. It was originally used as a model to investigate the orbital motion [2] of planetary objects. The famous scientist Christiaan Huygens first computed its time period and made it useful for timekeeping [3] three centuries ago. Understanding of some variants of a conical motion is also useful in designing some of the amusement park rides.

In this project, an answer is sought to a very simple but fundamental question of whether a conical pendulum can be excited parametrically. In other words, the possibility of resonance in a conical pendulum is studied by vibrating its point of suspension sinusoidally in a vertical direction. The angular displacement θ and the angular velocity $\dot{\theta}$ become time dependent, if the conical pendulum is excited parametrically. In such cases, a viscous damping acts on the rod and the bob, in addition to the damping force at the pivot. Therefore, a . A velocity-dependent damping force is also included. It is found that the mathematical formulation of a conical pendulum with oscillation of its pivot is qualitatively different from the problem of a conical pendulum kept on a flat oscillating platform. An explicitly time-dependent damping term appears in the former case, which is qualitatively new. This term survives even if the rotation rate is made to vanish. The latter case is equivalent to the case of gravity modulation. The full nonlinear equation for a conical pendulum is considered when the point of suspension (pivot) oscillates sinusoidally. The dynamics of such a conical pendulum and the possibility of resonance are investigated numerically. The results show interesting dynamics and the possibility of parametric excitation in narrow bands of forcing frequency of the point of suspension of the conical pendulum.

Summary

The dynamics of a parametrically excited conical pendulum is investigated by oscillating the point of suspension sinusoidally in a vertical direction. A study has been done on the single pendulum with a point of oscillation vibrating sinusoidally and also rotating. The equation of motion has been derived using Lagrangian formalism and a damping term has been added (Rayleigh's dissipative term). Limit cycles have been drawn and analyzed.

Equation of motion

Fig:1

The point of oscillation oscillates with ' $a \cdot \sin(\omega t)$ ' and the pendulum rotates with the frequency of ' Ω '

Fig:2

Lagrangian of the motion

$$x = l \sin(\theta) \cos(\Omega t)$$

$$y = l \sin(\theta) \sin(\Omega t)$$

$$z = l \cos(\theta) + a \sin(\omega t)$$

$$L = (\text{kinetic energy}) - (\text{potential energy})$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} m v^2 - mgh$$

$$\Rightarrow L = \frac{1}{2} m l^2 \dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} l^2 \Omega^2 \sin^2(\theta) + m a l \omega \dot{\theta} \sin(\theta) \cos(\omega t) + \frac{1}{2} m a^2 \omega^2 \cos^2(\omega t) - m g l \cos(\theta) - m g a \sin(\omega t)$$

Therefore the equation of motion from the Euler Lagrange equation is

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\theta}} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta} + Q = 0$$

Where Q is the dissipative force and is given by

$$Q = \frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{\theta}}$$

$$F = \frac{1}{2}\Gamma v^2 \quad [\text{Rayleigh dissipation function}]$$

And Γ is the damping coefficient

$$F = \frac{1}{2}\Gamma[l^2\dot{\theta}^2 + l^2\Omega^2\sin^2(\theta) + 2a\omega l\dot{\theta}\sin\theta\cos(\omega t) + a^2\omega^2\cos^2(\omega t)]$$

Therefore the equation of motion in theta is given as

$$\ddot{\theta} + 2\beta\dot{\theta} + [\omega_0^2(1 - A\sin(\omega t) + 2\beta a\frac{\omega}{l}\cos(\omega t) - \Omega^2\cos(\theta))]\sin(\theta) = 0 \quad \dots\dots(I)$$

here:

$$2\beta = \frac{\Gamma}{m}$$

$$\omega_0^2 = \frac{g}{l}$$

$$A = a\omega^2/g$$

I have integrated this equation(I) in Matlab using ODE45 which is a six stage, fifth order Runge-Kutta method.

Analysis of Limit cycles

I have integrated this equation(I) in Matlab using ODE45 which is a six stage, fifth order Runge-Kutta method.

First let's put the following variables to see the normal behaviour

$$\Omega=0, \omega=0, a=0, \beta=0.2$$

Fig(3)

So, it follows damped oscillations as expected

I've plotted the θ and $\dot{\theta}$ vs time also the limit cycles which are just the two dimensional phase space closed figures of θ vs $\dot{\theta}$. The figures that I've plotted all over the entire project are the sustained oscillations that is the the transient time has not been plotted. The sustained oscillations for most of the values are pure sinusoidal both in θ and $\dot{\theta}$ vs time. Also there are certain values like ($\Omega=2, \omega=5.4, a=0.2, \beta=0.4$) see Fig(4) at which the phase space is complicated and cuts at various points because it's a two dimensional projection of higher dimensional phase space.

If the frequency ω lies in one of the two resonance window peaks(which i'll discuss next) and the amplitude of oscillations of the pivot is above the cutoff(which i'll also discuss later on) value, and only if the value of β is small enough that we get to see the sustain periodic oscillations. The results are interesting only when we take damping into account

So in the following plots I've kept ' Ω ', ' ω ' and ' a ' as constants and ' ω ' lies within the resonance peak and ' a ' above the cutoff value and changed only β as 0.2, 0.4, 0.5.

Changing β only

$$\Omega=2, \omega=5.4, a=0.2, \beta=0.2$$

Fig(3)

$$\Omega=2, \omega=5.4, a=0.2, \beta=0.4$$

At this particular value of b we get interesting result

Fig(4)

$$\Omega=2, \omega=5.4, a=0.2, \beta=0.5$$

Fig(5)

Resonance

For a certain range of frequencies, we can see the amplitude increases with increase in 'a' and there is a jump discontinuity in the plots both at the onset of oscillations and at the termination of oscillations. There are two regions in the frequency domain where the amplitude gets very large. In the first region, the oscillations are pure sinusoidal and phase space consists of general ellipse type as can be seen in Fig(7) and the phase space for the second region is bit complicated as can be seen in Fig(8)

The peak value of the amplitude curves depend on the initial conditions or more precisely on the energy of the system. Higher the energy provided to the system, larger will be the peak value of both amplitude windows. I've taken two such plots for different initial conditions:

- 1) $\theta = 0.5$ and $\dot{\theta} = 0$ see Fig(6)
- 2) $\theta = 0.5$ and $\dot{\theta} = 0.4$ see Fig(9)

Fig(6)

Here the initial conditions are $\theta = 0.5$ and $\dot{\theta} = 0$

- $\Omega = 3,$
- $w_0 = 3.13,$
- $a = 0.13,$
- $\beta = 0.03.$

Fig(7)
Region 1 at $w = 3.13$

Fig(8)
Region 2 at $w = 6.12$

Here the initial conditions are $\theta = 0.5$ and $\dot{\theta} = 0.4$

$$\Omega = 3,$$

$$w_0 = 3.13,$$

$$a = 0.13,$$

$$\beta = 0.03.$$

Fig(9)

Here I've kept all the parameters same and only changed the value of 'a'

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega &= 3, \\ \omega_0 &= 3.13, \\ \mathbf{a} &= \mathbf{0.18}, \\ \beta &= 0.03.\end{aligned}$$

Region 1 at $\omega=3.13$

Region 2 at $\omega=6.8$

Cutoff amplitude of oscillation

There is a cutoff amplitude in the non zero amplitude window below which the amplitude becomes zero. I've plotted for different values of omega the amplitude of response vs. the amplitude of oscillations.

Here we can see that the cutoff amplitude of oscillation a_c depends on ω . Also the cutoff increases with increase in ω .

MATLAB Program

The following program that I wrote uses MATLAB's ODE solver for plotting second order differential equations.

```
function [yprime] = parametric_pendulum(t,y)
l=1; m=1 ; g=9.8;w0=3.13;Q=3;w=3.4;a=0.3;;b=0.03;
A=a*w*w/g;
y_prime=zeros(3,1);
yprime(1)=y(2);
yprime(2)=-2*b*y(2)-
(w0*w0*(1-A*sin(y(3)))+(2*b*a*w*cos(y(3)))/l)-Q*Q*cos(y(1))*sin(y(1))
yprime(3)=w;
yprime=yprime';
end
```

```
clc
close all
clear all
%-----Parameters-----
l=1; m=1; g=9.8;Q=3;w0=3.13;w=3.4;a=0.3;b=0.03;
A=a*w*w/g;
%-----initial condition-----
tspan=1000;
theta1=0.5;
theta1_prime=0.4;
z_0=0;
y0=[theta1 theta1_prime z_0];
[t,y]=ode45(@parametric_pendulum,[0,tspan],y0);
```

```
% eliminating the transient time
```

```
x=t(2500:3000);
```

```
r=y(:,2);
```

```
z=y(:,1);
```

```
g=z(2500:3000);
```

```
p=r(2500:3000);
```

```
%-----visualizing the result-----
```

```
figure(1)
```

```
%plot(x,g,'b')
```

```
plot(x,g,'b')
```

```
xlabel('time(t)','fontSize',14);
```

```
ylabel('theta(b) & theta-prime(r)','fontSize',14);
```

```
title('simple pendulum with damping','fontsize',14)
```

```
hold on
```

```
plot(x,p,'r')
```

```
%hold on
```

```
figure(3)
```

```
%plot(g,p,'b')
```

```
plot(g,p,'r')
```

```
xlabel('theta','fontSize',14);
```

```
ylabel('theta-prime','fontSize',14);
```

```
title('Phase space for simple pendulum with damping','fontsize',14)
```

Conclusions

The conical pendulum can be excited parametrically when the frequency of the pivot, ω , lies in a frequency band around

- (i) the natural frequency of the swing $\omega_0 = g/l$ and
- (ii) twice the swing frequency. The phase space plots show interesting behaviour including period tripling. The slope of the narrow band shows an increase when the frequency of externally imposed oscillation becomes equal to the frequency of rotation of the conical pendulum.

References

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- [2] Nauenberg, Michael (2006). "Robert Hooke's seminal contribution to orbital dynamics", *Robert Hooke: Tercentennial Studies*. Ashgate Publishing. pp. 69–420. ISBN 0-7546-5365-X.
- [3] "Horologium Oscillatorium: sive de motu pendulorum ad horologia aptato demonstrationes geometricae ([Latin](#) for "The Pendulum Clock: or geometrical demonstrations concerning the motion of pendula as applied to clocks"), dedicated to [Louis XIV of France](#))
- [4] R.W. Leven, B.P. Koch
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Plagiarism Report

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